

ISic3608

I.Sicily inscription 3608

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Priolo Gargallo, hypogeum A, contrada Monachella

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Priolo Gargallo, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645681

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 57.0902

Bommara, T., Rizzone, V.G. 2007. Contributo alla conoscenza del territorio siracusano: recenti indagini a Priolo Gargallo. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Vitale, E. (eds.), *La cristianizzazione in Italia fra tardoantico e altomedioevo*. Palermo. pp. 1647-1672. At 1659

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